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PRO PLANET

Enhanced Safe and Sustainable coatings for supporting the Planet

SECOND PRESS RELEASE

Our Cluster kick-off meeting

The first cluster meeting of the No-PFAS coatings sister projects commenced on May 14th, 2024. Partners from BIO-SUSHY, ZERO, PROPLANET, and TORNADO projects gathered for this initial meeting, united by a shared objective of developing PFA-free alternative solutions. The discussions were centered around each project's goals and strategies for future collaboration. It was a great opportunity to see different perspectives over our common no-PFAS target as well as to discuss the common challenges we are facing. This meeting provided a valuable platform for sharing insights, potential solutions, and fostering cooperative efforts among the projects.

A lot of dissemination & communication ideas were shared during this meeting and it was truly inspiring to see all members actively interacting with each other. As sister projects, we often target similar conferences to participate, which can lead to multiple partners reconnecting in relevant events, such as at MaterialsWeek, and we look forward to future collaborations. Special thanks are extended to the BIO-SUSHY team for their excellent organisation of the event.

Cluster kick-off meeting

14 May 2024, Online

As a united cluster, we want to assist each other in achieving our goals and to facilitate ongoing collaboration & communication. Therefore, a dedicated room on Microsoft Teams was created, serving as a central hub for the No-PFAS community to share ideas and alternative solutions around common challenges we are facing and to exchange useful files. This group room will help us maintain continuous engagement throughout the duration of the projects.

TORNADO

New routes of safe and sustainable by design water and oil repellent biobased coatings

Grant agreement ID: 101091944

The TORNADO project aims to transition to a safe circular economy by designing, producing, and treating products for end-of-life in sustainable ways. It will develop new PFAS-free, organic and hybrid coatings with water and oil repellence, adhering to Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) criteria. The project will research and develop two types of functionalised acrylated biomonomers and formulate biobased coatings using waterborne and hybrid sol-gel technologies. These coatings will be scaled up and validated in industrial environments to match the performance of traditional PFAS coatings. Their environmental impact and circularity will be assessed through comprehensive Life Cycle Assessments. Additionally, computational tools will be developed to predict necessary properties and toxicological endpoints.

BIO-SUSHY

Sustainable surface protection by glass-like hybrid and biomaterials coatings

Grant agreement ID: 101091464

The BIO-SUSHY project aims to develop innovative, repellent organic and hybrid coatings to replace polluting polyfluorinated alkyl substances, aligning with the EU's strategic goals for emerging technologies. The project will create hydrophobic and oleophobic coatings using bio-based thermoplastic powder and hybrid sol-gel technologies, enhanced with bio-based additives. These coatings will be validated on various substrates at a pre-industrial scale in sectors such as textiles, glass, cosmetics, and food packaging. A tailored Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) strategy will assess material toxicity, hazardous leachate, and life cycle impacts. This will be supported by modelling tools for predicting coating properties and leaching mechanisms, integrated into a comprehensive computational tool for data management and dissemination. The project will also address certification and standardisation, with stakeholder involvement to ensure social acceptance and economic impact.

ZeroF

Development of verified safe and sustainable PFAS-free coatings for food packaging and upholstery textile applications.

Grant agreement ID: 101092164

The ZeroF project aims to develop safe and sustainable-by-design (SSbD) coatings to replace PFAS compounds in food packaging and upholstery textiles. These coatings will feature limited water absorption and high oil/grease resistance for packaging, and high water and oil repellency for textiles. The coatings will be created from cost-effective precursors, maintaining costs within a 20% increase over current alternatives and targeting a 25% improvement in environmental impact. Renewable feedstock and non-toxic compounds will be used, replacing PFAS with cellulose fatty acid esters for packaging and silane-based hybrids for textiles. The project includes chemical development, formulation, coating, and validation, along with SSbD analysis of environmental impacts and toxicology. Computational methods will model toxicology and performance, aiding in certification and regulatory processes. The consortium includes research and industrial partners covering both packaging and textile value chains.

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